

Does the Quantum Wavefunction Follow from a Fourier Series Treatment of a Classical Potential?

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In classical physics, there is a potential $V(r)$ for a conservative force and force is linked to changes in momentum through Newton's second law. For the sake of argument, imagine one may write $V(r)$ as a Fourier series i.e. $\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ and attribute physical relevance to this series. In other words, $V(r)$ is a kind of average of microscopic granular system in which each $\exp(ikx)$ can impart momentum on a quantum particle. In addition, the Fourier series seems to have the appearance of a vector with $\exp(ikx)$ as a basis. It may also be noted that $\exp(ikx)\exp(ipx) = \exp(i(k+p)x)$. Thus, the potential seems to consist of 'particles' represented by $\exp(ikx)$ which may merge with quantum particles represented by $\exp(ipx)$ to form a boosted quantum particle $\exp(i(p+k)x)$. At first, it may seem $\exp(i(p+k)x)$ represents increased kinetic energy, but actually this merge should create potential energy. This perhaps gives a microscopic picture of potential energy. Thus, a merge of a Fourier series of $V(x)$ with an ensemble of quantum particles $\sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$ yields:

$$V(x) \sum_p f_p \exp(ipx) \quad ((1))$$

A point which arises, however, is that $\sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$ cannot represent physical density because it may be negative at certain x . Thus, ((1)) is a departure from classical physics in which the potential energy is $V(x)$ for one particle or $V(x)$ density(x). ((1)) represents a kind of potential energy interaction, but introduces a new ensemble object $\sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$ which does not seem to exist in classical physics. This ensemble also seems to be a vector. The objective of this note is to try to determine properties and conditions which arise from this merge. In particular, we wish to find an equation satisfied by $W(x)$ and also see how the classical picture is linked to this alternative scenario.

Fourier Series

Writing a function as a Fourier series is a mathematical process which need have physical relevance. Nevertheless, there are cases for which there seems to be physical relevance. For example, sound or other signals may be associated with Fourier basis functions $\exp(ikx)$. In addition, photons may be associated with Fourier basis functions and combine to produce a picture. In quantum mechanics, it is argued in textbooks the Fourier series of the wavefunction represents the possibility of a quantum particle being in one particular physical free momentum state or another. The Fourier series of the physical density, however, does not seem to have physical meaning in terms of momentum. A question which often arises regards the use of a wavefunction in quantum mechanics, when the so-called physical observable is probability density i.e. the wavefunction squared for a bound state. It seems that if one writes a classical potential in terms of a Fourier series, and suggests this series has physical meaning, then one is led away from classical ideas and towards quantum ones. In one dimension:

$$V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \quad V_k \exp(ikx)$$

One may suggest $\exp(ikx)$ represents a physical entity. Mathematically $\exp(ikx)\exp(ipx) = \exp(i(k+p)x)$, thus one may have an interaction with the potential which changes the momentum state of a quantum particle represented by $\exp(ipx)$. In general, one may wish to create an ensemble for the quantum particle which mimics the Fourier series for the potential, namely:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \quad f_p \exp(ipx).$$

$W(x)$ cannot be a physical density because it may be negative at points. Nevertheless, it represents the possible interaction of a quantum object with a potential and should somehow be related to potential energy. In classical physics, however, potential energy is $V(x)$ or $V(x)\text{density}(x)$.

Identity of $\exp(ipx)$

If $\exp(ipx)$ has physical relevance, it may be associated with a physical momentum state of a quantum particle. Like in classical physics, a potential changes momentum values. One may consider the interaction of the potential with $W(x)$ and write it in terms of basis functions $\exp(ipx)$:

$$V(x)W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \quad \left(\text{Sum over } k \quad V_k f(p-k) \right) \exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

Each $\exp(ipx)$, however, should represent a quantum particle in a p momentum state, thus there should be a classical kinetic energy of $p^2/2m$ for each $\exp(ipx)$. Note: In ((2)), one has an expression for a kind of potential energy, but this potential energy actually contains particles with kinetic energy.

One may write:

$$V(x)W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \quad B_p f_p \exp(ipx) \quad ((3)) \quad \text{where } B_p f_p = \left(\text{Sum over } k \quad V_k f(p-k) \right)$$

Furthermore, equations ((2)) and ((3)) seem to apply at a point x . When written in terms of ((3)), B_p seems to have the appearance of a potential energy. Thus, at a point x , one might try to write the total energy for a quantum particle momentum state:

$$p^2/2m + \text{Sum over } k \quad V_k f(p-k) = \text{energy}(p) \quad ((4))$$

((4)) is a dynamical equation, as quantum particles in different states $p-k$ combine with the potential states k to form p states. These in turn combine again with the potential to create other momentum states. Thus, ((4)) seems to represent a kind of average over time.

Matters become complicated, however, because each momentum state is multiplied by $\exp(ipx)$. This factor is part of the Fourier series of $V(x)$ and cannot be disregarded. From classical physics, kinetic energy $(x) + \text{potential energy}(x) = E$. If one multiplies by W :

$$KE(x) W(x) + V(x)W(x) = EW(x) \quad ((5))$$

Then, it seems that ((4)) becomes:

$$p^2/2m + \text{Sum over } k \text{ } V_k f(p-k) = E \quad ((6))$$

This seems to represent a kind of resonance equation which links all quantum particle momentum states to a single E. It should be noted that ((5)), however, leads to an unusual expression for KE(x)W(x) namely:

$$KE(x)W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } p^2/2m f_p \exp(ipx) \quad ((7))$$

Thus, probability weights proportional to $f_p \exp(ipx)$ are used. This represents probability which may be negative as well as complex. Thus, although each momentum state has a usual kinetic energy of $p^2/2m$, the overall average is very different.

If one examines ((7)), it has the form of vector and $\text{Sum over } p \text{ } f_p \exp(ipx)$ is another vector. Furthermore, f_p may be negative.

One may note that ((5)) is of the form of an eigenvalue equation. It seems kinetic energy and $V(x)$ are operators which disrupt the ensemble vector $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } f_p \exp(ipx)$. In this picture, taking the dot product of ((5)) with $W(x)$ and imposing the condition $W(x) \text{ dot product } W(x) = 1$ where the integral over x is the dot product, seems to show that overall kinetic and potential energy. In other words:

$$KE = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } f_p^2 p^2/2m \quad \text{and} \quad PE = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } f_p \text{ Sum over } k \text{ } V_k f(p-k) \quad ((8))$$

Thus, overall kinetic energy and potential energy seem to take on a physical role with respect to the ensemble vector $W(x)$. In the case of kinetic energy, each momentum state p represents an energy of $p^2/2m$ and this changes the ensemble vector, but one takes the dot product with $W(x)$ to measure, in a sense, the change relative to the $W(x)$ vector and thus finds the overall kinetic energy. In classical physics, a particle is in a state p at x at t and then changes as one moves in x and t . In the quantum picture, the state at t seems to be the ensemble vector $W(x)$. One measures its change due to an operator such as kinetic energy or potential energy, but then measures the overall change through a dot product with $W(x)$ itself.

Ultimately, ((5)) shows the disturbance of the kinetic energy plus potential energy operators on the ensemble $W(x)$ is equal to E times $W(x)$. Thus, it seems again that there is a resonance picture i.e. the ensemble is being bothered in such a way that it only scales.

Link with Physical Density

Given that multiplying ((5)) by the vector $W(x)$ yields physical kinetic energy and potential energy (one may divide the RHS by W^2), it seems W^2 may then be considered physical density if one wishes to retrieve the classical situation of $V(x)$ density(x) as representing a potential energy density.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems attributing physical meaning to a Fourier series of $V(x)$, leads to different physics from the classical picture. It seems one is led to multiply the Fourier series of $V(x)$, which has the appearance of a vector with $\exp(ipx)$ as a basis, by a vector $W(x) = \text{Sum } f_k \exp(ikx)$ for the quantum particle. This vector seems to

represent an ensemble for the quantum particle. This in turn appears to lead to a dynamical microscopic picture of various momentum states of the quantum particle $\exp(ikx)$ combining with states of the potential $\exp(ipx)$ to form, even for an instant, an overall state $\exp(ijx)$. This state $\exp(ijx)$, however, seems to represent a momentum j and so should have classical kinetic energy of $j^2/2m$. If one multiplies the classical conservation equation $KE(x) + V(x) = E$ by $W(x)$, it seems that one has a vector eigenvalue equation with kinetic energy and potential energy disturbing the ensemble vector $W(x)$. For example, KE operating on W yields: $\sum_k k^2/2m f_k \exp(ikx)$. In order to have a resonance, the overall disturbance simply scales W by E . Multiplying again by W seems to yield overall energy densities of the classical picture, suggesting that $W^2 = \text{density}(x)$.